

CADMIUM SALTS OF ORGANIC ACIDS

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Several salts of cadmium have been prepared by treating an aqueous solution of cadmium chloride with an aqueous solution of the alkali salt of the acid and also by heating anhydrous cadmium chloride with the acid; their properties have been studied and structures discussed.

Pickering (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 244) obtained cadmium salts of citric, tartaric and malic acids by mixing aqueous solutions of a soluble cadmium salt and the potassium salt of the acid. Grosmann and Jager (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1916, 78, 48) prepared cadmium acetate-4 ammonia, cadmium formate-3 pyridine, and cadmium formate-1 phenylhydrazine. Dubsy and Tritilek (*Chem. Listy*, 1935, 29, 76) studied the reaction of aminobenzoic acids with cadmium and zinc salts and found that a solution of the free acid did not react with the cadmium salt, but on addition of sodium acetate only the *ortho*-acid gave a precipitate. In the case of *para*-acid, a basic salt $[\text{COOK. Cd}(\text{COONH}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ was obtained on neutralisation with KOH. Gebauer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 176, 283) prepared acetylides, $\text{CdC}_2 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_2$, by passing acetylene through a solution of $\text{CdCl}_2 \cdot \text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{Ph}$ in acetone.

As a very few cadmium salts with organic acids were reported in the literature, the present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the conditions of preparation and properties of some of them.

EXPERIMENTAL

The acids and cadmium chloride used were of B.D.H. 'Pure' quality.

General Method of Preparation.—The cadmium salts were prepared by two methods.

(i) A saturated solution of cadmium chloride was mixed with a concentrated solution of sodium salt of the acid when a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed free of electrolytes and dried in an air-oven.

(ii) In this case two series of experiments were carried out; in one case an excess of the acid and in the other, an excess of CdCl_2 were used.

A mixture of cadmium chloride and the acid was heated on an oil-bath till the evolution of HCl had ceased. The product was washed free of the acid or CdCl_2 , as the case may be, and dried. Cadmium was estimated as cadmium sulphate and the organic matter obtained by difference. The same compound was obtained in all the three cases.

TABLE I

Cadmium salts of organic acids.

Acids.	Mol. formula of the Cd salts.	Colour.	M.P.	% Cadmium.		% Organic matter (by diff).	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Benzoic	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO})_2$	White	280°*	28.88	29.08	71.12	70.92
Salicylic	$\text{Cd}[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO}]_2$	Pale white	242°*	31.82	31.89	68.18	68.11
Phthalic	$\text{Cd}[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{COO})_2]$	Greyish white	272°	40.22	40.66	59.78	59.34
Cinnamic	$\text{Cd}[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCOO}]_2$	White	260°	27.87	27.66	72.13	72.34
Citric	$\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2\text{COO} \\ \\ \text{C}(\text{OH})\text{COO} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{COO} \end{array} \right] \text{Cd}_3$	Pale white	153°	46.89	47.15	53.11	52.85
Lauric	$\text{Cd}[\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_{10}\text{COO}]_2$	Milky white	101°	21.10	21.96	78.82	78.04
Myristic	$\text{Cd}[\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_{12}\text{COO}]_2$	White	94°	18.99	19.79	81.01	80.21
Palmitic	$\text{Cd}[\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_{14}\text{COO}]_2$	„	282°	17.93	18.03	82.07	81.97
Stearic	$\text{Cd}[\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_{16}\text{COO}]_2$	„	134°	12.98	13.16	87.02	86.84
Maleic	$\text{CdOOC}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{COOCd}$	Ash	260°*	66.01	66.27	33.99	33.73
Tartaric	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CdOOC} \quad \text{COOCd} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{CH}(\text{OH})_2 \end{array}$	„	242°	62.20	62.48	37.80	37.52

*—Decomposed.

From the results it is evident that cadmium behaves consistently as a divalent element and displaces the H of the carboxylic group in the salt formation. No basic salts were obtained in any of the cases studied. In the case of hydroxy-acids, viz., citric, salicylic and tartaric acids, the H of the hydroxyl group was not replaced even when CdCl_2 was in excess. The salts are stable in atmosphere, not easily decomposed by dilute acids or by water.

Thanks are due to Dr. S. S. Joshi, D.Sc., Head of the Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, for providing necessary facilities.

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Received January 1, 1958.